

Exploring Discourse Markers for Automated Argument Mining in Student Essays

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Abstract: This paper explores Natural Language Processing (NLP) in automatic comprehension and discourse analysis, focusing on argument mining. While previous works have focused on English, this study addresses the lack of adequate corpora and methodologies for Brazilian Portuguese. The researchers employed a corpus of essays from Brazil's National High School Exam (ENEM) to investigate the impact of discourse markers on identifying argumentative structures using feature engineering with machine learning. The proposed methodology offers key advantages over transformer-based approaches: enhanced interpretability of feature selection, computational efficiency, and improved adaptability across different linguistic domains. By systematically 'opening the black box' of machine learning models, this approach provides insights into the discourse marker identification decision-making process, in contrast to the opaque neural network models. Unlike the transformers-based solutions, this approach offers a transparent solution based on feature engineering allowing insights into the linguistic patterns underlying argumentative structures in Portuguese. While acknowledging the relatively small corpus size as a limitation, the researchers suggest that future work should focus on expanding the dataset for further evaluation. This work lays the groundwork for advancing NLP in Portuguese by providing valuable features and methodologies for feature engineering in automated linguistic analysis tasks such as essay scoring, opinion mining, and text summarization. The findings demonstrated a significant breakthrough, revealing that a concise set of only five argument mining-derived features dramatically improved the model accuracy, surpassing the performance of an initial, extensive set of over 600 features. These features specifically enhanced the evaluation of Competence 5, which assesses students' ability to develop intervention proposals grounded in scientific concepts.

Keywords: Argument mining, Features Engineering, Automated Essay Scoring, Natural Language Processing (NLP)

Categories: I.2.7, M.0

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1 Introduction

Natural Language Processing (NLP) encompasses knowledge representation, planning, perception, and learning [Mathur & Dinesh, 23]. It finds application in speech recognition, syntactic parsing, semantic analysis, discourse processing, and argument mining. Argument mining aims to identify the argumentative structure present within texts. Mining arguments from essays involves coherence, cohesion, discourse analysis, and argument structure identification. Effectively performing argument mining on essays requires a comprehensive analysis of coherence, cohesion, and the underlying argumentative structure [Stede & Schneider, 22].

Several works in the literature address this topic, employing complete end-to-end approaches that utilize NLP techniques and machine learning. The tasks involved include identifying argumentative/non-argumentative units, classifying units (thesis, arguments, proposals), and recognizing relationships between units [Stede & Schneider, 22]. The main approaches are component classification, relation identification, a combination of these tasks, and an end-to-end approach. However, these works primarily focus on English, highlighting the need for additional corpora and techniques tailored to Brazilian Portuguese.

This work focuses on essays from Brazil's National High School Exam (ENEM), which evaluates students' writing skills across five competencies. For the writing portion, two reviewers independently assign scores from 0 to 2 for each of the five competencies described in Table 1.

Competence 1	To demonstrate mastery of the formal written mode of the Portuguese language.
Competence 2	To understand the essay prompt and apply concepts from various areas of knowledge to develop the theme within the structural limits of the dissertation-argumentative prose text.
Competence 3	To select, relate, organize, and interpret information, facts, opinions, and arguments to defend a point of view.
Competence 4	To demonstrate knowledge of the linguistic mechanisms necessary for constructing argumentation.
Competence 5	To develop an intervention proposal for the problem addressed while respecting human rights.

Table 1: Descriptions of the competence evaluation criteria for grading ENEM essays

The emphasis lies on discourse processing, which involves analyzing longer texts composed of multiple sentences, such as argumentative essays. Comprehending discourse in essays necessitates assessing textual coherence and cohesion [Aluísio & Pinheiro, 22]. Automatic identification of arguments and argumentative structure within essays can be highly valuable for teachers, students, and applications [Stede, 19]. For instance, it could aid teachers and essay graders automate assessment tasks aligned with the ENEM competencies.

During the ENEM evaluation process, two reviewers independently assign scores ranging from 0 to 2, in 0.5 increments, for each of the five competencies. A score of 0 indicates that the author does not demonstrate mastery of the competence in question,

while a score of 2 indicates mastery. If there is a 1-point discrepancy between the scores assigned by the two reviewers, a third reviewer analyzes the essay. If the discrepancy persists after the third review, the essay is evaluated by all three reviewers [Gonçalves, 11].

This work employs a feature engineering-based approach to develop algorithms for the automated grading of competencies C2 and C5 of the ENEM (Brazilian National High School Exam). Unlike black-box transformer models, our methodology provides a transparent and interpretable framework for analyzing argumentative structures, offering clear insights into the discourse marker identification decision-making process.

Concurrently, it analyzes the impact of incorporating features obtained through argument mining on the results achieved by the classification algorithms. A training corpus comprising 50 annotated essays was utilized, and the argumentative elements in these essays were identified by linguists from the university's Master's program in Literature. This preliminary study investigates the potential of argument-mining techniques for evaluating argumentative essays in Portuguese, focusing on enhancing model interpretability and understanding.

The proposed approach was evaluated using common metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F-measure, with promising initial results highlighting the method's ability to provide transparent linguistic insights. Future work will expand the dataset to validate and refine the methodology, further exploring the advantages of feature engineering in automated linguistic analysis.

2 Background

This chapter presents the study's theoretical foundation, covering three main areas. First, it explores argument mining, its tasks, and applications in argumentative-discursive texts, emphasizing the context of ENEM. Next, it addresses machine learning, focusing on supervised classification techniques, particularly Support Vector Machines (SVM) and Gradient-Boosted Trees. Finally, it discusses recent advances in deep learning applied to argument mining, including Recurrent Neural Networks and transformer-based models. While this study focuses primarily on machine learning and feature engineering results, transformer-based approaches are presented in this section as they represent state-of-the-art avenues for future research.

2.1 Argument Mining

According to Stede and Schneider [Stede, 19], argument mining is an application of Natural Language Processing (NLP) that involves a set of tasks adapted to the type of text being analyzed. In essays, the thesis, arguments, and intervention proposals are extracted. Scientific articles typically include objectives, justifications, related works, and results. Therefore, argument mining is not a unified process, depending on the specific argumentative structure of the text.

Argument mining consists of seven tasks: *(i)* identifying argumentative text; *(ii)* segmenting the text into argumentative units; *(iii)* identifying the main claim; *(iv)* identifying the function of components; *(v)* identifying relationships between

components; (vi) constructing the structural representation; and (vii) identifying type and quality of the argumentation [Stede, 19].

Figure 1 shows that the fragment "We need to tear down this building" indicates an assertion by the author about a certain subject. The proposition "it will be expensive" contradicts this assertion. However, there is a counterargument in the fragment, "but the degree of contamination is no longer tolerable," refuting the previous objection. With the proposition, "Besides, it is one of the ugliest buildings in the city," another argument supports the initial statement about the need to tear down the building.

Figure 1: Example of argumentative structure [Stede, 19]

The essay required for the National High School Exam in Brazil demands the production of a discursive-argumentative text about a previously defined social, scientific, cultural, or political theme. When writing the essay, it is necessary to present a thesis, that is, an opinion about the proposed theme. This thesis needs to be supported by well-grounded arguments. In addition, it is necessary to elaborate a proposal for social intervention for the presented problem, respecting human rights [INEP, 17]. Figure 2 illustrates the steps for writing the essay in the ENEM model, the main instrument applied in Brazil to assess high school students' writing skills.

Figure 2: Process of developing an ENEM writing model

According to Stede and Schneider [Stede, 19], the classification of Argumentative Discourse Units (ADUs) can be applied to the entire text or specific excerpts, such as paragraphs and sentences. The segmentation into sentences has limitations since ADUs can span multiple sentences or be smaller than one. Thus, the ADU is part of a text with a unique role in the argumentation. After identifying ADUs, the next task is

classification into argumentative labels (claim, premise, etc.) via binary or multi-class classification problems. In addition to classification by sentence, sequence labeling approaches (IOB) separate non-argumentative text and detect claims.

The author can persuade the reader in various ways. To achieve this, the text provides statements and arguments. Identifying only the argumentative components is insufficient. It is necessary to map the relationships between them correctly. There is no consensus on how to describe the structure of an argument. The approaches can be summarized hierarchically and sequentially. The hierarchical structure relates argumentative units, forming a tree or graph. The sequential, linearly arranged units influence the rhetoric. In the hierarchy, there are proposals to build the structure: rule-based analysis, segmented classification, minimum spanning tree, integer linear programming, and artificial neural network [Stede, 19].

Integrating Natural Language Processing (NLP) with argument-mining techniques is a new frontier in automated linguistic analysis, particularly within the educational context. Recent studies by Nadeem et al. [23] and Zhang et al. [24] highlight the promising potential of these methodologies for evaluating and understanding argumentative texts.

This technological convergence emerges as an innovative response to traditional challenges of textual analysis, enabling a deeper and more systematic understanding of argumentative structures. Advances in machine learning algorithms and natural language processing make it possible to identify argumentative elements and analyze coherence, rhetorical strength, and discursive strategies employed in different textual genres. Such an approach transcends mere mechanical text classification, proposing a contextualized interpretation that considers linguistic nuances, semantic variations, and underlying argumentative strategies, becoming a crucial tool for researchers, educators, and text analysts.

2.2 Machine learning

Machine learning is the ability of agents to acquire knowledge through interaction with the environment, which is essential for intelligent behavior. During the process, agents must modify themselves with experiences. Learning occurs through experience, employing inductive learning and generating generic conclusions from examples [Luger, 08; Russell, 20].

Machine learning is typically classified into supervised, unsupervised, and reinforcement learning. Supervised learning occurs by observing labeled examples with input and output data. In unsupervised learning, the algorithm receives only input data and must identify patterns and extract knowledge. In reinforcement learning, the algorithm learns through reinforcement.

Argument mining in essays involves several machine-learning tasks. In this research context, supervised learning for classification tasks is most relevant. Identifying argument elements and relating arguments can be framed as binary classification - a sentence may be argumentative, and two arguments may or may not have a relation. Identifying argument types is a multi-class problem, where the algorithm must separate data into four classes: *(i)* thesis, *(ii)* argument, *(iii)* proposed intervention, and *(iv)* non-argumentative. Argument mining in student essays leverages supervised learning and classification algorithms to extract argumentative structures and relationships.

Support Vector Machines (SVMs), introduced by [Haykin, 99], are supervised machine learning techniques for linear classification or regression problems. SVMs aim to construct a hyperplane that separates positive and negative examples with maximum margin, as illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Optimal hyperplane for linearly separable patterns [Haykin, 99]

Rather than minimizing error, SVMs maximize the distance between the hyperplane and the nearest data points of each class. This technique builds an optimal separation boundary that accurately categorizes new examples with minimal misclassifications. Overall, SVMs are a powerful machine learning algorithm for classification tasks.

Statistical learning theory is used in SVMs to approximate the ideal classifier. Given a training set, the learning technique creates multiple model solution hypotheses and establishes mathematical conditions for selecting a certain classifier [Awad et al., 22]. SVMs implement structural risk minimization (SRM) [Haykin, 99].

Algorithms using this method tend to yield better generalization performance on unseen data. Despite not incorporating problem domain knowledge, SVMs can achieve good generalization performance for classification problems.

Problems are not always linearly separable. The SVM algorithm must be adapted to address these issues in such cases. SVMs perform mapping of the training set inputs into a new higher-dimensional space. In the case of two-dimensional inputs, the algorithm processes them into a new three-dimensional feature set [Awad et al., 22]. This allows a hyperplane to be found that separates the classes.

The different kernels in the SVM (Support Vector Machine) algorithm are functions that allow mapping the input data to a higher-dimensional feature space, where it is possible to find an optimal hyperplane for separating the classes. Each kernel has its characteristics and is suitable for different problems. The linear, Polynomial, RBF, and Sigmoid kernels were employed in this work, briefly described below.

- I. Linear is a simple supervised machine learning model that performs linear regression or classification by assuming a linear relationship between the features and the target variable. It is a fast and easy-to-train classifier with limited ability to

capture more complex nonlinear relationships. It is a good initial option for linear problems before trying more sophisticated algorithms. Its simplicity, speed, and lack of need for such data make it attractive for certain prediction and classification problems [Hastie et al., 09].

- II. Polynomial is a supervised learning algorithm for regression and classification that fits data to a polynomial function [Fitzgibbon et al., 21]. It finds the coefficients best fitting the relationship between input features X and output y . For classification, the Polynomial divides the space into regions based on the polynomial, assigning each region to a class. It is simple, computationally efficient, and can handle non-linearity but risks overfitting if the polynomial degree is too high. The Polynomial is a straightforward and fast option for linear and mildly non-linear problems.
- III. The Radial Basis Function Network (RBF) uses radial activation functions like Gaussian to create smooth approximations for nonlinear mapping [Pérez-Cruz et al., 20]. As a feedforward artificial neural network, the RBF typically contains an input layer, a single hidden layer with radial basis functions, and an output layer. The overlapping radial basis functions in the hidden layer allow the network to universally approximate nonlinear functions and achieve complex nonlinear mapping from the input to output space. The RBF can model any nonlinear function given sufficient radial basis functions in the hidden layer.
- IV. Sigmoid is a popular binary classifier that models the probability of a sample belonging to a class using the sigmoid logistic function [Rawat, 22]. It adjusts weights to minimize classification error via gradient descent. The Sigmoid can handle non-linear data separations. Advantages include easy interpretation of predicted probabilities and fast convergence. Drawbacks include the susceptibility to overfitting and plateauing problems during training. The Sigmoid is used in various binary classification applications, such as spam and anomaly detection.

Gradient boosting [Yang & Li, 22] is a machine learning technique that builds an ensemble of weak prediction models, typically simple decision trees, to create a strong predictive model. Unlike traditional boosting methods, gradient boosting optimizes an arbitrary differentiable loss function, using the gradient of the loss function to guide the training of the weak learners.

The key idea behind gradient-boosted trees is to sequentially add new decision tree models that predict the residuals or pseudo-residuals from the previous iteration. This allows the ensemble to focus on the most difficult-to-predict cases, gradually improving the overall model performance. Gradient-boosted trees have been shown to outperform other ensemble methods like random forests across diverse applications [Chen & Guestrin, 16].

Compared to other ensemble methods, gradient-boosted trees often demonstrate superior predictive power, as the sequential training process allows the model to adaptively focus on the most informative features and patterns in the data. The resulting gradient-boosted trees model is a powerful and flexible machine-learning algorithm that can be applied to diverse regression and classification tasks [Hastie et al., 09; Natekin & Knoll, 13].

2.3 Features Engineering

Feature engineering is a crucial preprocessing step in supervised machine learning and statistical modeling [Sharma et al., 2012]. This process transforms raw data into a more effective set of inputs, each with several features. Feature engineering can significantly improve the predictive accuracy and decision-making capabilities of the models by providing them with relevant and informative features.

One important application of feature engineering is the clustering of feature objects or sample objects within a dataset. Techniques based on matrix decomposition, such as Non-Negative Matrix Factorization (NMF) [Lee & Seung, 99], Non-Negative Matrix-Tri Factorization (NMTF) [Wang et al., 11], and Non-Negative Tensor Decomposition/Factorization (NTF/NTD) [Lim & Comon, 09], have been extensively used for data clustering under non-negativity constraints on the feature coefficients. These non-negativity constraints yield a part-based representation of the features, and the resulting factor matrices exhibit natural clustering properties.

Several extensions and variations of these feature engineering methods have been proposed in the literature to address inherent issues and improve their performance. For example, orthogonality-constrained factorization can achieve harder clustering, while manifold learning techniques can be incorporated to overcome challenges associated with the original algorithms [Zhang et al. 22; Jing & Yang, 22]. These advancements in feature engineering have enabled researchers to extract more meaningful and informative features from complex datasets, leading to enhanced performance in a wide range of machine learning and data analysis tasks.

2.4 Transformer Models in Argument Mining

Over the past decade, argument mining has experienced substantial advancements propelled by breakthroughs in deep learning. The advent of transformer-based models has revolutionized this field. These sophisticated architectures have yielded remarkable results across various natural language processing tasks, demonstrating exceptional prowess in identifying and analyzing complex argumentative structures. Their ability to capture nuanced linguistic patterns and contextual relationships has opened new avenues for more accurate and efficient argument-mining techniques.

In recent years, transformer-based models have revolutionized the field of natural language processing. These models, such as BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) [Devlin, 18], RoBERTa (Robustly Optimized BERT Pretraining Approach) [Liu, 19], and XLMNet [Yang et al., 19], employ sophisticated attention mechanisms to decode intricate semantic relationships between words and phrases, capturing nuances that eluded previous approaches.

A key advantage of these models is their versatility in pre-training on vast multilingual corpora and subsequent fine-tuning for specialized tasks like argument mining. This transfer learning capability is particularly beneficial when working with smaller datasets, a common scenario in many argument mining applications.

Ruiz-Dolz et al. [21] demonstrated the effectiveness of transformer-based models in automatically identifying argumentative relations across different domains. Their study revealed that these models consistently outperformed traditional machine-learning approaches in argument-mining tasks, underscoring their potential to advance the field.

Further exemplifying the adaptability of these models, Mayer, Cabrio, and Villata [Mayer, 20] explored their application in healthcare-related argument mining. Their research highlighted the transformers' capacity to navigate complex, specialized domains, opening new avenues for automated analysis in fields with distinct linguistic challenges.

3 Related Works

Argument mining represents a critical frontier in Natural Language Processing (NLP), focusing on automatically identifying and extracting argumentative structures within text. This chapter explores recent methodological advances in argument component detection, structural parsing, and machine learning techniques applied to argumentative text analysis. The presented works demonstrate diverse approaches to understanding argumentative discourse, ranging from joint extraction of argument components to sophisticated parsing techniques in various textual contexts, particularly student essays. By examining these approaches, we provide a comprehensive overview of the current state-of-the-art in argument mining research, highlighting innovative strategies for automatic argumentative structure identification.

3.1 Joint extraction of argument components and relations

An approach to unite two argument-mining tasks: component classification and component relation [Du, 17] The authors argue that the component classification stage has high accuracy, but the error rate increases in the next task, relating the components. According to the authors, this is the propagation of errors, as errors in the classification reflect the relationship. The authors believe that the problem can be mitigated by combining tasks. The authors propose to join the arguments in pairs so that the information about the type of components and their relationship is in the class; for example, in the class "C – S – MC," the first component, a declaration, provides support for the second element which is an important claim. Therefore, the algorithm will assign a class specifying the type of the first and second elements and their relationship.

Each argument pair contains three feature parts for learning: source component features, direct component resources, and mutual information resources. In the construction of resources, four categories of resources were used: (i) structural resources, (ii) lexical resources, (iii) syntactic resources, and (iv) indicator resources.

The authors used four algorithms for the tests: (i) Logistic Regression, (ii) Random Forest, (iii) Decision Tree, and (iv) Support Vector Machine. The essay database used by the authors contains 402 essays in English on various topics, consisting of 7,116 sentences and 147,271 words (tokens).

The high dimension of 9098 features made the authors use feature selection algorithms. The algorithm chosen was Information Gain. The authors employed 10-fold cross-validation, and the evaluation of the algorithms is measured with precision, recall, and F-value rates. An initial test was performed using logistic regression to verify the best number of resources. According to the authors, syntactic resources contributed negatively to the experiment. Five hundred features were used to test all algorithms. Logistic Regression presented the best result of the algorithms tested with an F-value of 0.6081, precision of 0.5958, and recall of 0.6209. Finally, the authors

conclude that the result of the new approach of combining two mining tasks into a single task is comparable with the literature, in which the tasks are treated separately.

3.2 Parsing argumentation structures in persuasive essays

Stab and Gurevych [Stab, 14] present an end-to-end approach for English essays, in which they identify the boundaries of argument components, perform classification, and, finally, relate the components. The authors used a sequential word-level labeling approach to delimit the boundaries of argument components. The first word of an argument was marked as “Arg-B,” subsequent words as “Arg-I,” and non-argumentative words as “O.” To classify each word into one of these classes, the authors used Conditional Random Fields (CRF) with averaged Perceptron training. Features such as structural, syntactic, lexical-syntactic, and probability-based were extracted for each word. The algorithm achieved an F1-score of 0.867, a precision of 0.873, and a recall of 0.861. The F1 scores were 0.809 for “Arg-B,” 0.934 for “Arg-I,” and 0.857 for “O.”

The authors trained classification and argument relationship models locally. For both tasks, SVMs with polynomial kernels and feature sets were used. Consequently, results may not be globally consistent. For instance, the relationship identification model failed to connect 37.1% of assumptions in experiments. To minimize errors, the authors present a joint model that globally optimizes the outputs of the two base classifiers using Integer Linear Programming (ILP). For each paragraph with n components, unmatched outputs were entered as claims, and the remaining components as premises.

Finally, the authors classified the type of argumentative relationship in a binary task, categorizing each relationship as supporting or attacking. For this task, they used SVMs and six sets of features: (i) lexical, (ii) semantic, (iii) syntactic, (iv) structural, (v) rhetorical, and (vi) word embeddings. The resulting F1 scores were 0.947 for support relations, 0.413 for attack relations, and 0.680 overall.

3.3 Argument mining with structured SVMs and RNNs

Niculae, Parl, and Cardie [17] proposed an approach to unify argument mining processes, in which the authors developed a new factorial graph model to classify components and their relationships. The model proposed by the authors supports parameterizations with SVM and Recurrent Neural Network (RNN). The training and testing corpus contained 402 annotated persuasive essays in English.

The factorial plot was used to bring a new approach to the problem of argument mining, as most efforts focused on tree or forest structures. However, according to the authors, argumentation by nature may be less well-formed, indicating low syntactic precision. For example, the argument may have a simple tree structure and a more complex graphical structure.

To parameterize the potentials of unary and higher-order factors, the authors used SVM and RNN. SVM was used with a set of features from Stab and Gurevych [Stab, 14], with the `pystruct4` library, the regularization parameter $C \in \{0.001, 0.003, 0.01, 0.03, 0.1, 0.3\}$ and optimization of the average between the link and proposition scores by F-Value. For the RNN, the authors parameterized the factor graph potentials based on Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM). The more general AD3 algorithm

replaced MST inference. The authors used cross-validation, adjusted the dropout probability in the dense layers of the multilayer perceptron (MLP) above {0.05, 0.1, 0.15, 0.2, 0.25} and the optimal number of passes over the training data at {10, 25, 50, 75, 100}. Two layers were used for the LSTM and the proposition classifier, 128 hidden units in all layers, and a multilinear decomposition with classification $r = 16$.

The tests were carried out with three variant factor graphs, basic, complete, and strict, in addition to a baseline. The SVM algorithm with full configuration presented the best average of the mining tasks, with an *F value* of 68.9. For identifying propositions, the RNN with strict configuration presented an *F value* of 79.3 as the best result. The SVM baseline with strict variation in link identification presented a 60.3 *F-value*.

3.4 Improving argument mining in student essays by learning and exploiting argument indicators

Argument mining enables a systematic analysis of texts' rhetorical and logical structure, going beyond traditional evaluation methods. Research by Palau & Moens [22] highlights that automated identification of discourse markers can reveal complex argumentative patterns that manual analyses frequently overlook. Contemporary approaches combine machine learning with linguistic analysis to identify argumentative structures, evaluate coherence and argumentative quality, and provide detailed feedback on argumentative competencies.

Nguyen and Litman [Nguyen, 15] present a study that examines the usefulness of resources used in literature and proposes new resources on topics in the essay domain. It further performs evaluations using 10-fold cross-validation and topic domain validation. The authors' corpus contains 90 annotated essays in English. The authors implemented Stab and Gurevych [Stab, 14] and Nguyen and Litman [Nguyen, 15] as baseline features.

The model proposed by the authors contains the features contained in Nguyen and Litman [Nguyen, 15] and four new features: (i) many common words between the given sentence, its previous sentence, and the title of the essay; (ii) comparison words: two binary characteristics that indicate the presence of comparative and superlative adverbs; (iii) five binary characteristics that indicate whether each of the five first-person plural pronouns is present; and (iv) three binary characteristics that show whether each of the discursive relations of comparison, contingency, and expansion is present.

The models were trained with the Sequential Minimal Optimization (SMO) implementation of SVM in the Weka tool with the top 100 features ranked by the Information Gain algorithm. The authors' approach obtained the best results for testing separate essays on domain topics and the entire essays. For tests carried out on separate domains, the authors found accuracy, kappa, precision, and recall values of 0.807, 0.675, 0.771, and 0.722, respectively. The results for the entire set were 0.805, 0.673, 0.763, and 0.720, respectively.

The results show that the features proposed by the authors significantly improve argument mining performance across the entire set of trials and trials separated by domains. Furthermore, the performance of various essay topics indicates that the model developed is even better than the performance of all the essays.

4 Development

This chapter presents the methodological framework for argument mining, detailing the comprehensive approach to developing an automated argument extraction system. The chapter systematically explores the processing steps involved in creating an effective argument-mining algorithm, beginning with the corpus construction methodology and progressing through the intricate development of algorithmic strategies. By delineating the technical procedures from corpus preparation to algorithm design, this chapter provides a transparent view of the research's methodological rigor and the systematic approach employed to advance argument-mining techniques for linguistic analysis.

4.1 Processing steps

The processing steps were developed based on the work of Stab and Gurevych [Stab, 14]. Figure 4 shows the processing steps. From an input essay, it is necessary to segment the text into sentences and, from them, perform feature extraction. The obtained features are the inputs to the component and relationship classifiers. Finally, the argumentative structure is constructed and optimized through integer linear programming.

Figure 4: The system processing steps adapted from Stab and Gurevych [Stab, 14]

4.2 Building the corpus

The corpus construction process went through two stages:

- I. 50 essays were randomly extracted from the National High School Exam (ENEM) from the Brazil Escola website. This portal contains an essay database where students can submit texts on specific topics and receive expert feedback.
- II. Subsequently, the essays were annotated by two independent experts from the graduate program in education [Haendchen Filho et al., 19]. The BRAT annotation tool [Stenetorp et al., 12] was used specifically for text annotations.

The annotation task consisted of six steps: (i) definition of argument elements and specifications; (ii) annotation of components; (iii) analysis of component inconsistencies; (iv) annotation of argumentative relations; (v) analysis of relation inconsistencies; and (vi) preparation of the final corpus.

The Component and Relation annotations were done separately to avoid error propagation in annotator divergence. First, the components were annotated, divergences analyzed, and a corpus was compiled with the argumentative units. Finally, the relations were annotated, divergences verified, and the final corpus version was produced. Table 2 shows the correlation between the reviewers' annotators for each component, measured by Krippendorff's α coefficient [Krippendorff, 13].

Component	α
Thesis	0,87
Argument	0,91
Intervention Proposal	0,95
Relations	0,72

Table 2: Agreement between reviewers for components

The annotation of the components had an overall average correlation of 0.92. The coefficient ranges from 0 to 1, where 0 indicates no inter-rater correlation, and 1 indicates complete inter-rater correlation. It is possible to observe the high agreement between the annotators for the arguments and intervention proposal components among the annotated components. However, the thesis presented the lowest agreement between the evaluators. Relationship annotations showed the lowest level of agreement among annotators, with an overall average agreement of 0.72. Because of this, analyzing relationship inconsistencies required more time and attention to evaluate discrepancies between annotators in the third person. Table 3 presents the final corpus statistics.

	Total	Average per essay
Phrases	659	13,18
Words (tokens)	20659	413,18
Theses	62	1,24
Arguments	222	4,44
Intervention Proposals	100	2
Non-argumentative	275	5,5
Relations	407	8,14

Table 3: Final corpus statistics

4.3 Development of argument miner algorithms

This section outlines the process for implementing algorithms to extract the argumentative structure of an essay. It covers (i) implementing the algorithms for segmentation and feature extraction. (ii) classifier training and validation, and (iii) Implementation of Integer Linear Programming. These procedures are described below.

Python 3.7 was chosen for development due to its extensive NLP and ML libraries. Microsoft Visual Studio Code 1.35 was used as the IDE.

Segmentation and feature extraction

Text segmentation was performed by dividing the essay into individual sentences to enable further analysis. The NLTK library was utilized to implement this segmentation. Morphological analysis and feature extraction were conducted using NLTK, CoGrOO, and other libraries. The extracted features were like those used by Stab and Gurevych [Stab, 14], with three exceptions - discourse, probability, and PMI features were excluded as comparable tools for Portuguese were not identified. Furthermore, Stab and Gurevych extracted different feature sets for each mining task, whereas the same core feature set was extracted here for component classification. Table 4 outlines the features extracted for this task.

Type	Description	Used tools
Lexical	These features include lemmatized unigrams and the two thousand most frequent dependency word pairs limited to bigrams.	CoGroo and NLTK
Structural	Consists of statistical metrics based on the components, including the number of words (tokens) in each component, whether the component is first or last in the paragraph, the relative position within the text, and others.	NLTK
Indicators	It is based on the manual extraction of four lexical indicators: advanced, regressive, thesis, and refutation.	Indicators were translated, and their identification was implemented in Python.
Contextual	It involves extracting the context of an argument component by analyzing the preceding and following sentences. Specifically, the previous four indicators are extracted from these contextual sentences. Four additional features are collected that identify shared verb or noun phrases between the component and the introduction/conclusion.	The contextual indicators were translated, and their identification was implemented in Python.
Syntactic	It is based on the distribution of grammatical classes within the component. Specifically, it extracts the depth of the parse tree, the tense of the main verb, and the presence of auxiliary verbs in the component.	CoGroo and SpaCy
Word Embeddings	These consist of features extracted based on pre-trained word embeddings. Each word's vectors in an argument component are summed across subsequent words and added to the feature set.	Word2Vec CBOW 300 dimensions.

*Table 4: Extracted feature groups for component classification.
Source: Adapted from [Stab, 14]*

The feature implementations were carried out in Python using libraries. Features that depend on the word list, such as indicators, were adapted according to Brazilian Portuguese. Finally, each argument has a set of resources for defining its class and subsequent learning. In relationship identification, learning is by pairs of components; therefore, the set of features is extracted from the two components; in addition, shared features, such as the shared nouns feature, are also extracted.

Classifier training and validation

Training and validation were performed using sci-kit-learn, a machine-learning library developed in Python. This library already contains the Support Vector Machine (SVM) algorithm implementations. The parameter settings of the classification algorithms were defined with a default value.

In the tests, the algorithm was cross-validated using 5-fold and 10-fold techniques, along with various metrics to evaluate the results, such as accuracy, macro precision, macro recall, and macro-F-score. The 5-fold cross-validation indicates five iterations of training and testing the algorithm with different subsets of the data. It partitions the corpus into five distinct subsets, where one subset is used for testing, and the remaining four are used for training. This process is repeated five times, each subset serving as the testing set once.

For instance, in the first iteration, the first one-fifth of the essays are used for testing, while the remaining four-fifths are used for training. In the second iteration, the second one-fifth of the essays are used for testing, the rest for training, and so on, until all five subsets have been used for testing. Similarly, the 10-fold cross-validation follows the same principle. Still, the corpus is partitioned into ten subsets, and the algorithm is trained and tested ten times, with each subset serving as the testing set once.

The source codes of this work were made available on an internet version control platform to support new research in argument mining in Brazilian Portuguese and to allow the reproduction of the tests performed in this study. The corpus used in this work differs in size and language from those used in the articles selected in the systematic literature review, which may impact the results. The performance calculations were elaborated according to the practices observed in the literature and obtained through specialized libraries.

5 Results

This section presents the individual results obtained for the `Component` and `Relation` classifiers. The metrics used for evaluation were accuracy, macro-precision, macro-recall, and macro-F score, which were chosen based on the work of Stab and Gurevych [Stab, 14].

The `Component` includes the following classes: (i) *Thesis*, (ii) *Arguments*, and (iii) *Intervention Proposal*. This means the essay is being evaluated to determine whether it has a thesis, arguments, and intervention proposal for the exposed topic. `Relation` indicates if there are relationships among the phrases. Table 5 shows the results for each metric, classifier, and kernel used.

		Kernel			
		<i>Linear</i>	<i>Polynomial</i>	<i>RBF</i>	<i>Sigmoid</i>
Component	<i>Accuracy</i>	0.585	0.630	0.675	0.400
	<i>F-score</i>	0.581	0.620	0.655	0.141
	<i>Precision</i>	0.622	0.670	0.685	0.100
	<i>Recall</i>	0.596	0.624	0.665	0.250
Relation	<i>Accuracy</i>	0.924	0.910	0.951	0.951
	<i>F-score</i>	0.535	0.598	0.487	0.487
	<i>Precision</i>	0.539	0.589	0.475	0.475
	<i>Recall</i>	0.540	0.623	0.500	0.500

Table 5: Classifier results (5-fold)

In classifying the *Component*, the RBF kernel performed best with the essay components, with an *Accuracy* of 0,675, *F-score* of 0,655, *Precision* of 0,685, and *Recall* of 0,665. For the *Relation* classification, the polynomial kernel presented the best F-score of 0,598. This indicator has a high accuracy of 0.91, which shows that accuracy alone may not be an accurate metric. The high accuracy in classifying relations is because there are no relations between sentences in most cases; there are 8,240 cases without relations against 407 relations, which is why the class imbalance is high for this classifier.

The *Component* classifier has three classes: *Thesis*, *Argument*, and *Intervention Proposal*. Table 6 shows the F-score results for these classes with the polynomial kernel, which presented the best F-score result for these attributes.

Approach	No argument	Thesis	Argument	Intervention Proposal
5-fold	0,551	0,491	0,671	0,744
10-fold	0,541	0,518	0,681	0,741

Table 6: F-score per class obtained by the polynomial kernel for *Component* class classification

The *Intervention Proposal* obtained the best result, being the most easily classified category. However, the algorithm failed to identify most of the essays' thesis correctly. Although there is usually one *Thesis* per essay, the same essay can present more than one *Intervention Proposal*. The identification of *No-Argument* sentences scored below *Argument* sentences, showing the ease of classifying the latter.

6 Applied Study

The applied study was conducted to validate the applicability of argument mining in automated essay-scoring systems. This involved the following steps: (i) corpus extraction and preprocessing, (ii) class balancing, (iii) model training, and (iv) model evaluation.

6.1 Corpus extraction and preprocessing

The corpus of essays was sourced from reputable platforms such as UOL and Brazil School portals. These platforms offer a wealth of evaluated essays with corrections, scores, and reviewer comments. Each essay is scored from 0 to 2, with increments of 0.5, across five competencies corresponding to the ENEM evaluation model.

To avoid noise in the automatic classification process, the following processing steps were performed: (i) removal of special characters, numbers, and dates; (ii) conversion of all text to lowercase; (iii) application of morphological markers (POS tagging) using the NLPNET library [Fonseca, 13]; (iv) token inflection through stemming using the NLTK library [Lane et al., 23] and the RSLP algorithm [Orengo, 01], specific to the Portuguese language; and (v) segmentation (tokenization) by words, sentences, and paragraphs. In addition to these steps, only essays with more than fifty characters and available scores for all competencies were considered. In total, 4,317 essays were collected, dated from 2007 to 2018.

6.2 Class balancing

The corpus used for the experiments has an unbalanced number of essays per grade, which can negatively affect the classifier's efficiency. Figure 5 shows the proportion of scores assigned to each category in Competencies 2 and 5. Each bar refers to a score, with 0 as the lowest grade and 2 as the highest.

Figure 5: Distribution of scores in competencies 2 and 5

The imbalance problem was solved using the ROS (Random Oversampling) technique. The classifier is trained until the desired class ratio is reached, and it is used to balance the class distribution by randomly multiplying the minority class to approximate the number of class labels becoming the distribution uniform.

6.3 Model training

For the training, a matrix containing 4,317 rows and 624 columns was created, where each row represents an essay and each column represents a feature, as shown in Table 7. The last column contains the score assigned by the human evaluator for the fourth or fifth competence.

The feature type Argumentative Structure appears in bold at the bottom of Table 7 and consists of 5 features. These features were introduced to test the effectiveness of the discourse marker model used to train the machine learning algorithm. During the algorithm's processing, the results will be evaluated with and without including these 5 'Argumentative Structure' features, highlighted in the bottom rectangle of Table 7. This approach will allow for an analysis of whether including these discourse marker-based features benefits the model's performance.

Feature type	Description
Lexical diversity and statistics (84 features)	Metrics indicate how varied the use of the lexicon is in textual production. They were calculated from the token type ratio and included content words, function words, verbs, adjectives, pronouns, paragraph size, paragraphs per sentence, and so on.
Bag of words (70 features)	A set of words based on an analogical dictionary, looking for categories of words that convey ideas such as cause-effect relationships, formation of ideas, comparison of ideas, hypothesis, cause, circumstance, purpose, conditional conjunctions, consequence, explanation, and so on.
Textual Coherence (179 features)	Coherence is achieved through syntactic features like anaphoric/cataphoric elements and logical temporal structure. Examples include sentence similarity in the first paragraph, justification markers, antithesis markers, and conclusion markers.
Textual Cohesion (187 features)	Various overlapping indices were calculated to identify referential cohesion relationships in the text. For example, the overlap of nouns and pronouns among adjacent sentences and paragraphs, the overlap of adjectives, verbs, adverbs, content words, and so on.
Adherence to the Theme (98 features)	Adequacy or relevance to the topic refers to how well an essay's content relates to the given thematic prompt. An adequate essay consistently maintains the theme introduced in the prompt and avoids irrelevant digressions.
Argumentative Structure (5 features)	Number of theses, arguments, intervention proposals, non-arguments and components (theses + arguments + intervention proposal).

Table 7: Feature dimensions

6.4 Model evaluation

Based on previous results obtained with different algorithms and data balancing techniques in the analyses of the ENEM for Competence 1 [Haendchen Filho et al., 19], the Support Vector Machines (SVM) and Gradient Boosting Trees (GBT) algorithms are used, which showed the best performances in this prior work. Each machine-

learning model was trained using the training set and the implementations provided by the sci-kit-learn library [Geron, 17] for the Python language. After the training step, the models were applied to the respective test sets of each evaluated competence, and the scores predicted by them were stored for each essay.

The first set of results aims to provide an overview of each machine learning model's performance in evaluating Competence 2. For this purpose, an analysis based on confusion matrices was performed, which facilitates visualization of the classification errors made by each model.

Since the dataset presented an imbalanced class distribution (grades), the values of each confusion matrix were normalized by row. This normalization was done by dividing each cell by the number of examples of that specific class in the complete training set. This allows for a fairer comparison between models, preventing classes with more examples from having a disproportionate weight.

Figure 6 shows the normalized results of the confusion matrices for Competence 2. The Matrices on the left represent the results without the five argumentative features, as per Table 7. The random undersampling (ROS) balancing method and the classification models (SVM and GBT) proved to be the only combination that could identify the extremes or high-quality essays with some reliability. However, it substantially decreases the model's predictive ability in the three intermediate classes (0.5, 1, and 1.5).

Figure 6: Confusion Matrix with grading distribution in Competence 2

For the evaluation of Competence 2, the results show that including the argumentative features described in the last group type of Table 7 does not significantly alter the performance of the two classifiers. This indicates that such evaluation is relatively independent of the number of arguments and the other characteristics of this type of feature.

The second set of results provides an overview of each model's performance in Competence 5, as illustrated by the respective confusion matrices in Figure 7. Like the previous figure, the left-hand matrices represent the results without the five argumentative features described in Table 7.

A comparison reveals that including these argumentative features significantly enhances the performance of both classifiers for this competence. The most notable improvement was observed for the maximum score (2.0) with the GBT classifier, where the true positive rate increased from 0.21 to 0.48 - a considerable gain given the relatively small number of essays classified with this top score. Moreover, the confusion matrices exhibited a more diagonal pattern when the argumentative features were incorporated into the models, indicating better performance.

Figure 7: Confusion Matrix with grading distribution in Competence 5

This study uses *k-fold* cross-validation to evaluate the performance of the machine learning models. Originally, each cycle of this approach randomly divides the available dataset into two subsets: a test set and a training set. The test set contains a fraction of $1/k$ of the data, while the training set contains the remaining $(k-1)/k$ data. stratified sampling was employed. With this variant, the distribution of classes (or grades, in this

case) present in the complete dataset is carefully maintained in the training and test subsets. This preservation ensures that both subsets mirror the characteristics of the original set, thereby allowing for a more accurate model evaluation. Using this methodology, it is possible to obtain a reliable estimate of the model's performance in a real environment, where the input data will have a distribution like the training data. A slightly modified version of the *k-fold* cross-validation strategy was used to measure the performance of each statistical model [Geron, 17].

7 Discussion

Studies such as Nguyen and Litman [15] demonstrated the efficacy of argumentative structures in enhancing automated essay-scoring systems. These findings substantiate the potential of argument-mining techniques for evaluating essays in Brazilian Portuguese. Ghosh et al. [24] report relevant results by applying NLP techniques that include improving accuracy on arguments classification and extracting discourse markers and offering insights into argumentative strategies.

The regulations for Brazil's ENEM exam define a maximum disagreement limit of 0.5 points between graders for each competence, considering a maximum score of 2.0 points. The scoring scale adopted for our corpus ranges from 0 to 2, with the threshold adjusted closer to 0.5. Therefore, predictions with an absolute deviation from the true score of less than 0.5 can still be considered accurate. Considering this, a set of graphs representing each combination's quality is produced. In these graphs, the vertical axis represents the "relaxed" proportion of correct predictions for each class, which is equivalent to the expression $y_i = C_{i,i} + C_{i,i-1} + C_{i,i+1}$, where C indicates the cells of the normalized confusion matrix.

Figure 8 shows that the measured accuracy for Competence 2, including argumentative features, is very similar to that without these features.

Figure 8: Relaxed proportion of correct predictions for Competence 2

Although the impact of the argumentative features applied in Competence 2 was not significant, it is understandable that evaluators consider other criteria besides argumentation to assign the grade. According to the ENEM Manual, Competence 2 aims to verify whether the student understood the essay prompt and applied concepts from related areas of knowledge to develop the theme within the structural limits of the argumentative dissertation text. Therefore, this competence goes beyond simply verifying the presence of an argumentative structure.

The research's results on the impact of the argumentative features applied to Competence 5 were highly relevant. As illustrated in Figure 9, the accuracy measured by the set of features, including the argumentative characteristics, was considerably higher than that obtained without them.

This difference becomes even more evident when analyzing the accuracy rates for scores 1 and 1.5, which showed a significant increase with the inclusion of the argumentative features.

Figure 9: Relaxed proportion of correct predictions for Competence 5

It is remarkable that a relatively small set, composed of only five features obtained through argument mining, had such an expressive impact on a set of more than 600 features. This result suggests that identifying and incorporating specific argumentative elements can provide valuable insights for evaluating Competence 5, which refers to developing intervention proposals supported by scientific concepts for the addressed problem.

It is important to consider that the evaluation criteria for Competence 5 are less susceptible to subjectivity than other competencies. The main criterion consists of verifying the presence or absence of a solid intervention proposal, considering the new argumentative features introduced. Within the five features extracted through argument mining, a specific one identifies the existence or lack of a well-structured intervention proposal.

This remarkable result suggests that a relatively small set of features created following formal procedures and objective criteria can significantly impact certain

evaluation domains. Despite representing only a fraction of the 600 features used, these five argumentative characteristics substantially affected the accuracy of the Competence 5 evaluation.

This finding reinforces the importance of adopting a systematic approach based on argument mining to identify and incorporate relevant features into machine learning models. By capturing key elements of the argumentative structure, such as premises, conclusions, and logical relationships, valuable insights can be obtained that potentially increase the accuracy of the evaluation, especially in domains where argumentation plays a central role.

8 Conclusion and future works

The argumentative-dissertation nature of the ENEM essays makes the presence of well-constructed argumentative structures crucial for demonstrating competence. Unlike black-box transformer models, our machine-learning approach offers a transparent methodology for assessing student performance by extracting and interpreting key argumentative features.

The applied study validated the applicability of argument mining for automated essay-scoring systems. By systematically analyzing premises, conclusions, and logical relationships, our feature engineering approach provides clear insights into the decision-making process of score prediction. The results demonstrate that a relatively small set of argument mining-extracted features can achieve significant gains in predicting assigned scores, especially for evaluating Competence 5's requirement of developing well-grounded intervention proposals.

This finding is particularly significant because constructing such proposals requires strong argumentative skills supported by scientific concepts. The methodology's interpretability allows for a more nuanced understanding of how researchers evaluate these skills, offering a transparent alternative to inscrutable neural network approaches.

The machine learning model gained valuable insights by extracting and utilizing features that capture essential argumentative elements. This successful study demonstrates the effectiveness of argument-mining techniques across different languages, paving the way for broader incorporation into automated evaluation systems.

Potential improvements for future research include:

- Expanding the dataset by increasing annotated essays to improve learning accuracy
- Developing new features for discursive markers specific to ENEM Competence 2

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